

DETERMINING THE PSYCHOSOCIAL PROBLEMS OF STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN PORT HARCOURT METROPOLIS OF RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: *This study examined the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The survey research design was adopted in carrying out the study, with the population of 1.080 students with hearing impairment from ten (10) Special Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The sample size of 292 respondents, which was determined using the Taro Yamen's formula, was drawn from 6 out of 10 schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State, through simple random sampling technique. A researcher design questionnaire titled Psychological Problems of Students with Hearing Impairment Questionnaire (PPSIQ) was used to collect the required data. The study concluded that it is the right of every child to receive equal opportunity for education. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that, parents should seek for help at the very early stage to avoid adverse effect on the child, since the manner at which students with hearing impairment develop psychological problems is no associated with its mode of inception.*

Keywords: *Psychosocial problems, Hearing Impairment, Gender.*

Introduction:

Impairments and other related problems of special needs affect lives of students who are directly or indirectly connected with it, sometimes severity in disabilities renders students impaired for life. Some of the disability cases are deep-seated and invisible, creating room for the spiritual undertone often associated with it. Hearing impairment or deafness involves not only the loss of hearing, but the limitation of the ability to naturally acquire language and speech which has serious implications for the student's development. Consequently, the negative effect of hearing loss on individuals could be very serious, if it is not well managed. When hearing impairment occurs before or after birth, it can create difficulties in the person's communication, adjustment and learning (Agomoh & Kanu. 2011).

If the social and environmental barriers are eliminated, students with disabilities would have a more realistic opportunity of living equally alongside students without disabilities. The psychosocial model of disability locates some possible external problems that may be faced by students with disabilities and these may affect their behavioral communication ability, self-esteem and self-image (Greenberg Kusché,

Gustafson, & Calderon, 2005). These challenges may be tackled through maintaining cordial relationship with persons with the disability. As such, the negative effects of hearing impairment on the students cannot be overemphasized, as hearing impairment affects virtually all aspects of the students' life. It is a serious handicapping condition that tends to isolate the child from normal living pattern, Furthermore, hearing impairment has been reported to have social and personality effect on the students; these ranges from communication barrier, stigmatization and poor self- concept amongst others (Moeller, 2007).

The Problem

The World Health Organization (2015) reports that 15% of the world's population is living with at least, one disability (up to 20% in resource poor settings) and that the number is increasing due to various factors including the rise in chronic diseases such as HIV/AIDS and other handicapping conditions in developing countries. Children with hearing impairment in Rivers State are less likely to be sent to school because of reasons ranging from financial issues, fears of not coping, worries in regards to stigma and its effect on the wider family such as siblings and other family members influencing parents' decision not to send their child with disability to school.

It is therefore not surprising that the International Disability and Development Consortium estimates that 98% of children with disabilities including children with hearing impairment in developing countries like Nigeria are denied formal education, social gathering and little attention. In addition, those children with hearing impairment who do not meet up their needs might have fewer demands placed on them, and therefore may learn less or experience social and psychological maladjustment than their peers without disabilities (Sahara Reporters, 2019).

The major emphasis in educating students with hearing impairment has been in enhancing communicative abilities while excluding many other aspects of social and mental development. In the light of potential adjustment problems that exist for many hearing- impaired students are, which ranges from onset of hearing loss, mood of communication. poor socio-economic background, hearing loss based on age and educational background, neglect by parents and society at large, there is a need for educators to become aware of and to adopt strategies for promoting positive and effective development of impaired students. All these problems limit social participation of students with hearing impairment. As such it is against this backdrop that this study was carried out to fill the gap. The state of the problem, therefore is to examine the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The general aim of the study is to examine the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

The specific Objectives of the study are as follows:

- To find out the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
- To ascertain the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender.

Research Questions

- ❖ What are the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
- ❖ What are the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender?

Conceptual Review

This study adopted the theory of social development by Erik Erikson.

Theory of Social Development

Erik H. Erikson a German psychologist trained in psychoanalysis under Anna Freud, (Sigmund Freud's daughter) between 1927 and 1933 divided social development into eight stages signifying "the eight phases of life" (Erickson, 1965). He asserted that at any point in life, the individual is the product of the way conflicts are resolved (Kinane, 2010). This implies that with positive experiences, children with hearing impairment could work through their challenges and develop skills like autonomy, trust, initiative and others to help them positively resolve the developmental challenges still ahead. If, however, children's attempts at problem resolution result in consistent failure, they will not be prepared for future challenges. Since Hearing loss has a negative impact on communication skills and, therefore, creates additional challenges it thus depends on Erikson's theory to succeed in rehabilitating such persons.

Erikson's Eight Stages of Psychosocial Development are summarized in the table below (Kinance, 2000):

Stage	Age period	Bipolar Crisis Stage	Equivalent Freudian Stage
1	Early infancy	Basic Trust vs. Mistrust	Oral
2	Later infancy	Autonomy vs. Shame & Doubt	Anal
3	Early childhood	Initiative vs. Guilt	Phallic
4	Middle child hood	Industry vs. Inferiority	Latency
5	Adolescence	Ego identity vs. Role confusion	Genital
6	Early adulthood	Intimacy vs, Isolation	
7	Middle adulthood	Generativity vs Stagnation	
8	Late adulthood	Integrity vs. despair	

Trust versus Mistrust

The task of the infant at this stage is to develop a basic sense of trust in self and the environment. The infant is completely dependent on others for satisfaction of needs. This has to be provided by adults, especially the mother or care giver. From birth through approximately 3 years of age, Erikson postulates

that children experience two distinct stages of psychosocial development. In the first stage, children learn whether they can trust their environment and if their basic needs will be consistently met (Barker, Quittner, Fink, et al 2009). When caregivers meet children's basic needs, children learn to trust them and their environment in general. Children with hearing loss may be at a disadvantage in this stage of development because of several factors. For example, their parents may not be able to respond consistently to their needs because they are experiencing grief over their child's diagnosis. A child may not have access to the auditory cues that signal that a parent's attention may be diverted (e.g., doorbell or ringing telephone) or not be aware of the auditory stimulation a parent is using to comfort the child or to show affection. In the absence of a feeling of basic trust, the infant develops a pattern of withdrawal and depression.

Autonomy versus Shame or Doubt

The second stage is centered on the task of anal muscular control and learning when it is appropriate to hold back and let go (Kinanee, 2010), Erikson indicates that when the child develops a sense of self-control, he or she also gains a sense of self-esteem and a lasting sense of good will and pride. But when there is parental domination, the child develops profound feelings of shame and doubts. At this stage, children from about 1 to 3 years of age are challenged to explore their environment and start to take some control over it (Barker, Quittner, Fink et.al 2009). Children with hearing impairment may be at a disadvantage for developing independence because they do not have access to developmentally appropriate tools in their environment such as the telephone, household alarms, door-knockers, or television. The children at this stage may be overprotected and not encouraged to try new activities or exert their independence making them to be helpless.

Initiative versus Guilt

For Erikson, the task of the third stage is the development of conscience. The child starts undertaking, planning and attacking tasks initiated by himself. With positive reinforcement and appropriate and consistent limitations, children will succeed in this stage. If their attempts result in failure or criticism, they can develop a sense of guilt for seeking independence and shame and doubt in their abilities (Hogan, Shipley, Strazdins, 2011). Schwartz (2000) opined that children with hearing impairment typically have very favorable opinions of themselves and their abilities. It is the duty of the audiologists, Psychologist, parents and other support groups to promote the healthy psychosocial and development of young persons with hearing impairment.

Industry versus Inferiority

The task here is that of winning recognition by producing things. The child is able to apply himself or herself to some tasks or skills and becomes absorbed in the process of producing. Energy is applied to self-improvement and conquest of things. He is full of energy and makes efforts to produce things. It also marks the beginning of social relations as the child engages in activities with others. Where the child lacks the requisite skills or finds himself worse than other children in their productive activity, he

may be discouraged and develop a sense of inadequacy and inferiority. This may be manifested in an attempt to isolate oneself (Barker, Quittner, Fink, 2009).

Identity versus Role Confusion

At puberty, the child is starting to see and identify that represents more than just accumulated childhood experiences. According to Erikson, ego identity is confidence that one's self is matched with other's perceptions of oneself, which ultimately becomes established in the promise of a career. Thus, the main task for the adolescents is that of integration of expression and experience into career. If the young person is unsure of his or her skills, sexual identify self-worth and so on, he or she experiences role confusion and so is unable to settle on an occupational identity. Erikson believes that it is in searching for self-identity that adolescents identify with popular figures (Erickson, 1963).

Intimacy versus Isolation

The task during this stage is that of establishing an intimate relationship with one another person, which requires having enough confidence to be able to lose a part of the self in order to fuse one's identity with another person (Barker, Quittner, Fink et.al 2009). Intimacy, commitment and affiliation are the hallmark of this stage. For those unable to reach for intimacy, isolation and destructive distancing ensue.

Generatively versus Stagnation

Generatively is the concern to establish and guide the next generation. It is a mature desire to be necessary to others in terms of providing guidance and encouragement. Thus, the person achieves satisfaction from being engaged by others and being consulted. This increases his confidence and sense of worth. Where there is not the case, he stagnates, that is, he sees himself as redundant. Little wonder, then, that one of the ways to undo or silence a "difficult" manager in an organization is to assign him to a section where he will have no body to manage or, render him redundant (Barker, Quittner, &Fink 2009).

Ego Integrity versus Despairs

The task of this stage is that of reviewing life's success and failures and preparing for death. It involves accepting one's life experiences as having been what they should be, becoming satisfied with one's achievements and failures. Where there is no ego integrity, there is only despair, resentment and fear of death (Barker, Quittner, & Fink, 2009).

Concept of Psychosocial Problems

The term psychosocial can be described as a connection between psychosocial aspects of experiences (including our thoughts, emotions and behaviour) and our wider social experiences such as: (Relationships, traditions and culture). Psychosocial problems can be referred to as challenges that can limit someone's ability to function effectively psychologically and socially in a regular society. The main characteristic of the hearing impairment is the limited ability to hear sound and its impact on language. Non responsive when talked to and difficulty in language expression are the two ways in which the

problem is manifested. Behaviours associated with these traits may range in asking for repetition of question, cupping of the ear in order to hear better, straying to hear and pitch problem which most times are descriptors to identify a hearing-impaired child (Ozoji. 2005)

The following are examples of psychological and social problems students with hearing impairment are likely to encounter:

Depression

Depression refers to a wide range of mental health problems characterized by the absence of a positive affect (a loss of interest and enjoyment in ordinary things and experiences), low mood and a range of associated emotional, cognitive physical and behavioural symptoms. Distinguishing the mood changes between clinically significant. The identification of major depression is based not only on its severity but also on persistence, the presence of other symptoms, and the degree of functional and social impairment. However, there appears to be no hard-and-fast "cut-off between 'clinically significant and 'normal' degrees of depression, the greater the severity of depression, the greater the morbidity and adverse consequences (Kessing, 2007).

Stress

Stress is a bodily reaction to stressors, consequently, complex interaction of systems of the body can result in deleterious consequences to those systems and organs to the point of a person becoming "stressed out"; and serious illness can follow. It also a feeling of emotional strain and pressure, it is any influence of internal and/or surrounding environment on living being which disrupt its homeostasis. Stress may be understood as a state of tension experienced by individuals facing extraordinary demands, constraints or opportunities. Stress is the spice of life and the absence of stress makes life dull, monotonous and spiritless (Corning. 2002).

Anxiety

Anxiety is the total response of a human being to threat or danger. Each experience of anxiety involves a perception of danger, thoughts about harm, and a process of physiological alarm and activation. From the learning perspective, generalized anxiety is precisely a product of stimulus generalization. Anxiety would thus become connected with almost any environment or situation, similarly, agoraphobia would represent a kind of generalized anxiety (Hollon, Stewart & Strunk, 2005). Anxiety would become triggered by cues associated with various social or vocational situations outside of the home in which the individual is expected to perform independently, as in travelling, going to work, and shopping. Panic attacks are also triggered by cues that are subtle and not readily identified. From the learning perspective, compulsive behaviours are operant responses that are negatively reinforced by relief of the anxiety engendered by obsession thoughts Phobias such as social phobias and agoraphobia involve cognitive processes usually related to an exaggerated appraisal of threat in social situations (excessive fears of embarrassment or criticism) or public places (perception of helplessness or fears of panic attack)

Frustration

Frustration is a key negative emotion that roots in disappointment (Latin frustra or "in vain") and can be defined as irritable distress after a wish collided with an unyielding reality. A functional perspective, the experience of brief and intense emotions is an integral component of our everyday conduct.

Emotions influence how we make decisions and navigate our worlds, via bodily changes that prompt us to action. Frustration is a key negative emotion that roots in disappointment, and can be defined as irritable distress in response to limitation, exclusion, and failure (a state of dissatisfied insecurity). Frustration elicits negative affect to signal that interests and interactions must be adjusted, and emotional tension or "arousal" to instigate defensive or aggressive behavioural responses such as strive to reduce or eliminate the blocking agent or circumstances.

Stigmatization

Stigmatization is when someone views you in a negative way because you have a distinguishing characteristic or personal trait that's thought to be, or actually is, a disadvantage (a negative stereotype). Unfortunately, negative attitudes and beliefs toward disable children are common. Several studies show that stigmatization usually arises from lack of awareness, lack of education, lack of perception, and the nature and complications of disability, for example odd behaviours (Abad, Fear day& Safdar, 2010). We focus here on what stigma is, and how it affects the thoughts, feelings, behaviour, and health of its targets.

Concept of Hearing Impairment

Hearing Impairment can be described as term which describes any condition that reduces the hearing sharpness of an individual and makes it difficult for the person to identify and understand auditory signal sounds. When the ear, auditory cortex and auditory nerves are not functioning well due to disorder or abnormality affecting it is when this condition appears. The major challenge facing students with hearing impairments is communication Hearing-impaired students vary widely in their communication skills.

Causes of Hearing Impairment

The causes of hearing impairment or hearing loss and deafness can be divided into two: Congenital and Acquired.

Congenital: Congenital causes may lead to hearing loss being present at or acquired soon after birth. Hearing loss can be caused by hereditary and non-hereditary genetic factors or by certain complications during pregnancy and childbirth, including maternal rubella, syphilis or certain other infections during pregnancy, low birth weight; birth asphyxia (a lack of oxygen at the time of birth); inappropriate use of particular drugs during pregnancy such as aminoglycosides, cytotoxic drugs, antimalarial drugs, and diuretics; severe jaundice in the neonatal period, which can damage the hearing nerve in a new born infant (Agomoh & Kanu, 2015). **Acquired:** Acquired causes may lead to hearing loss at any age after birth when the individual is already certified good in the sense of hearing; it is called acquired because it comes at some age due to the following factors:

- infectious diseases including meningitis, measles and mumps;
- chronic ear infections;
- collection of fluid in the ear (otitis media);

use of certain medicines, such as those used in the treatment of neonatal infections malaria, drug-resistant tuberculosis, and cancers, injury to the head or ear, excessive noise. including occupational noise such as that from machinery and explosions; recreational exposure to loud sounds such as that from use of personal audio devices at high volumes and for prolonged periods of time and regular attendance at concerts, nightclubs, bars and sporting events (Agomoh & Kanu 2015).

METHODOLOGY

The study will adopt the survey design in order to examine the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment. Anyanwu (2016) described survey design as a situation in which the researcher observes what happens to sample subjects without controlling them and it can be done at one or more points. It is appropriate because it will aid the researcher to use a set of structured questionnaires to elicit information on how the respondents think and feel about the study.

Findings

The figures below show the distribution and collection of questionnaires sent to the respondents with respect to the special needs schools used for the study. The result indicated that out 292 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed representing 100%. 288 copies of questionnaire retrieved were properly filled representing 98.76%, while 4 copies that were not properly filled representing 1.24% were discarded.

Questionnaire Distribution

S/N	Name of Special Needs Schools	Questionnaire Sent	No. Returned	%
1	Otana Inclusive Center (OIC)	53	52	98.11
2	Pleasant Place Child Educational Center 64 (PPCEC)	64	63	98.44
3	Hope Spring Inclusive School (HSIS)	56	55	98.21
4	Total Child Educational Center (TCEC)	45	44	97.78
5	The Child Educational Center (TCEC)	43	43	100
6	Shalom Inclusive International School (SIIS)	31	31	100
	Total	292	288	98.76

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2021).

Questionnaire distribution and retrieval analysis

Research Question One: What are the psychosocial problems of students with bearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Mean response of the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Respondent (n = 288)		
		X	SD	Decision
1	My condition always get me depressed	3.39	0.77	Accept
2	1 most times experience stress as a result of my condition	3.70	0.59	Accept
3	Most of the time I experience high level of anxiety	3.33	0.74	Accept
4	I am always frustrated when carrying out a task	3.53	0.64	Accept
5	I often experience stigmatization	3.36	0.60	Accept
6	1 often experience social isolation	2.83	0.99	Accept
7	I feel inferior to others	3.16	0.87	Accept
8	I find it difficult to relate with people	3.41	0.66	Accept
9	I feel am neglected by my class mate	3..31	0.75	Accept
10	I often feel am productive	3.20	0.90	Accept
11	My views and opinions are often resented by my peers	1.75*	1.04	Reject
12	I am always afraid of what people will say about me	2.64	1.22	Accept
13	Occasionally, I am always harassed by my classmates	1.69*	0.86	Reject
14	I feel like committing suicide at times	3.39	0.84	Accept
15	I find it difficult communicating with others	3.48	0.64	Accept
16	Sometimes, I may find it difficult to go along with others	1.89*	1.10	Reject
17	I feel abandoned because of my condition	3.38	0.71	Accept
18	I feel dented right because of my condition	3.39	0.63	Accept
19	1 am snubbed by my teachers	2.80	1.14	Accept
20	I do not feel I am giving the opportunity to contribute to the society just like every other person	3.27	0.80	Accept
Grand Mean		3.06		

Criterion Mean 2.5, Mean 2.5, Accept, Mean 2.5, Reject

Mean score **with** asterisk (*)-Indicates rejected item ($X < 2.5$)

Mean score **without** asterisk (*)-Indicates accepted item ($X \geq 2.5$)

The table shows the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result showed majority agreed to items 1-10, 12, 14,15, and 17-20 with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.5). On the other hand, majority of the respondents disagreed to 11, 13, and 16, with their mean scores less than the criterion mean (2.5). The grand mean of X 3.06 indicates that the psychosocial problems prevalent among students with hearing

impairment include among others, depression, stress, anxiety, frustration, stigmatization, social isolation and inferiority complex among others.

Research Question Two: What are the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender?

Mean response of the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender.

S/N	Items	Male (n=185)		Female (n=103)	
		X	SD	X	SD
1	My condition always get me depressed	3.39	0.74	3.38	0.81
2	I most times experience stress as a result of my condition	3.70	0.58	3.70	0.62
3	Most of the time I experience high level of anxiety	3.24	0.80	3.48	0.58
4	I am always frustrated when carrying out a task	3.48	0.67	3.62	0.58
5	I often experience stigmatization	3.63	0.62	3.62	0.56
6	I often experience social isolation	2.85	0.98	2.80	1.01
7	I feel inferior to others	3.12	0.85	3.24	0.90
8	I find it difficult to relate with people	3.42	0.63	3.39	0.72
9	I feel am neglected by my class mate	3.30	0.70	3.32	0.83
10	1 often feel unproductive	3.28	0.81	3.07	1.04
11	I am always afraid of what people will say about me	1.82*	1.08	1.63*	0.94
12	My views and opinions are often resented by my peers	2.70	1.23	2.52	1.20
13	Occasionally, I am always harassed by my classmates	1.65*	0.83	1.69*	0.90
14	I feel like committing suicide at times	3.33	0.85	3.50	0.80
15	I find it difficult communicating with others	3.44	0.64	3.53	0.62
16	Sometimes, I may find it difficult to go along with others	1.99*	1.14	1.72*	1.01
17	I feel abandoned because of my condition	3.36	0.73	3.43	0.68
18	I feel denied right because of my condition	3.36	0.61	3.44	0.67
19	I am subbed by my teachers	2.85	1.14	2.70	1.15
20	1 do not feel I am giving the opportunity to contribute to the society just like every other person	3.33	0.73	3.17	0.91
Grand Mean		3.06		3.05	

Criterion Mean 2.5, Mean \geq 2.5, Accept, Mean $<$ 2.5, Reject

Mean score **with** asterisk (*) - Indicates rejected item ($X < 2.5$)

Mean score **without** asterisk (*) - Indicates accepted item ($X \geq 2.5$)

The table shows the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender. Majority of the male students with hearing loss agreed to items 1-10, 12, 14, 15, and 17-20, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.5). On the other hand, majority of the respondents disagreed to 11, 13, and 16, with their mean scores less than the criterion mean (2.5).

Also, majority of the female students with hearing loss agreed to items 1-10, 12, 14, 15, and 17-20, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.5). On the other hand, majority of the respondents disagreed to 11, 13, and 16, with their mean scores less than the criterion mean (2.5).

The grand mean of $\bar{x} = 3.06$, for male student with hearing loss, and $\bar{X} = 3.05$, for female students with hearing loss, indicates that the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender.

Discussion of Findings

The study analysed the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The finding in table above showed that the psychosocial problems prevalent among students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State are; depression, stress, anxiety, frustration, stigmatization, isolation, inferiority complex, communication problem, peer pressure, amongst others. The finding of this study is consistent with the study of Okiridu (2018), whose finding indicated that children with usual and hearing impairment in special school experience psychological problems such as lack of physical integrity and shame, light and sound security. Spoken and written communication, confidence in ability of senses, feeling of being easily noticed, and feeling of dependency, frustration, sadness, stigmatization and discrimination amongst others.

Furthermore, the finding in table 2 shows that the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State do not differ substantially based on gender. Furthermore, table 2 shows that there is no significant difference in the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State based on gender. This finding is corroborated by Okiridu (2018), whose study found that there is no significant difference between the psychosocial problems of male and female with hearing impairment. Adding credence to the finding is Livingstone and McPhillips (2011). They found no significant association between gender and the gross motor skills of children. Furthermore, they noted that male students with hearing impairment exhibit behavioural disorders more often, but receive professional help than female students with hearing impairment who exhibit emotional disorder.

Conclusion

The study investigated the psychosocial problems of students with hearing impairment in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The finding from the study had revealed that students who suffer hearing impairment of any degree, irrespective of the onset of hearing loss or gender experience very high extent of psychosocial problem ranging from discrimination, aspersion, loss of focus, feeling

dejected, lonely, and feeling worthless. Based on the outcome of the study, it becomes necessary to put up viable and proactive steps to in order to provide professional who are seasoned in all Special Education centres to help counsel the students in order that their social and mental wellbeing will be pointing to the positive trajectory. Conclusively, it should be noted that hearing impairment can be properly managed when the right personal is tasked to do so, in a proper and conducive learning environment that will enhance learning. Therefore, children are gift from God, irrespective of their predicaments, if the right mindset is instilled in them, they are achieved what every normal human can also achieve.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and the implications thereof, the following recommendations are proffered:

- ❖ Parents should seek for help at the very early stage to avoid adverse effect on the child, since the manner at which students with hearing impairment develop psychological problems is no associated with its mode of inception.
- ❖ The Rivers State Government should provide equal preventive and recovery opportunities should be provided for both the male and the female, because the development of psychological problems among students with hearing impairment is not linked to the gender.
- ❖ There is need for parents, teachers and significant others to show love to their wards with hearing impairment. This will boost their sense of belonging in their environment; seeing that the development of psychological problems among students with hearing impairment is not related to the mood of communication.
- ❖ Government and the school administrations should make provision for the services of a professional guidance counsellor in special needs schools. The presence of school guidance counsellor will help in adjusting the students' personal-social, educational and vocational needs.
- ❖ Finally, In-service training should be provided for the counsellors and caregivers of students with hearing impairment in order to update their knowledge in the counselling and rehabilitation of their clients whose needs may vary as they develop in age.

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